

3D GESTURAL INTERACTION WITH HARMONIC PITCH SPACE

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an interface allowing users to intuitively interact with harmonic pitch space through gestures in physical space. Although harmonic pitch spaces are a well-defined concept within the circles of academic musicology, they often fail to engage with non-musicians or musicians outside academia. A three-dimensional *tonnetz* founded on root progression theories is conceived and a graphical representation rendered for visual feedback. Users navigate the tonnetz with two-handed gestures captured in three-dimensional space with a purpose built video colour-tracking system. Root transitions and pivot tone triads are used to navigate the tonnetz and trigger audio feedback generated with MIDI.

Keywords: Harmonic pitch space, Interactive, Gesture, Tonnetz, Root progression theory.

1. INTRODUCTION

In musicology, the construction of harmonic pitch spaces as cognitive models for music perception has been a fruitful area of research for the past four or so decades [1]. In particular, various tonnetz models have become a useful spatial metaphor for tonal, harmonic and pitch relations [1, 2, 8, 12, 13]. However, for musicians outside of musicological circles and non-musicians such constructs may seem unintuitive or abstract.

We present a new interface for three-dimensional, two-handed gestural interaction with a tonnetz model. Since the interface relies on simple gestures, it does not necessitate musical instrument skills or music theoretical knowledge but aims to allow users to intuitively explore the underlying principles of tonal harmony. As such, the interface has strong didactic properties and will be of interest to music educators and students, as well as a wider variety of performers, composers and even non-musicians.

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1.1. Related Works and Interfaces

The current paper aims to build on the work of several related studies and interfaces. Simon Holland's *Harmony Space* [6, 7] allows users to navigate a two dimensional tonnetz (Figure 1) with whole body gestures, working within the context of music education. The interactive system exists in two versions: [6] manually tracks users movements around a tonnetz projected onto a floor space and [7] captures footfalls and arm gestures with pressure sensors and accelerometers. *Harmony Space's* tonnetz, derived from a cyclic group theoretic model [8] for musical pitch, can be summarised as a two dimensional grid ordering pitches by major thirds along the horizontal axis and minor thirds along the vertical. Two further important intervallic pitch structures can be derived from the two diagonals, corresponding to fifth and semitone relations respectively. Pitch-nodes within a diatonic scale are visually marked. For example, in Figure 1 the seven diatonic tones of D major are underlined; *Harmony Space* uses black and white backgrounds to identify diatonic tones. [6, 7] are fundamentally didactic interfaces, placing strong emphasis on the understanding of music and harmony implicitly with the aid of gestures, a fundamental concept of the current paper.

Figure 1. A section of *Harmony Space's* tonnetz, ordered by major and minor thirds.

Similar matrix-based interfaces have been used to augment performance and improvisation on musical instruments [9]. Adeney's *HarmonyGrid* consists of four grids controlling musical parameters (volume, rhythm, timbre and harmony) with a four-by-four matrix covering a floor area of approximately two meters squared. Performers' motions are tracked with an overhead webcam,

triggering and controlling audio in real time. The system is optimised for musical performance, and therefore the chord layout does not reflect any music theoretical constructs.

A larger scale interactive interface for music education is presented in [10], tracking user location by GPS. A neo-Riemannian tonnetz governs physical distances between pitch-nodes with level of musical consonance. The planar tonnetz is mapped onto a physical space where pitch-nodes are placed approximately 80m apart and triggered when users entered an ‘influence’ radius for each node. Overlapping ‘influence’ radiuses allow users to trigger more than one node at a time, generating various dyads and major or minor triads. The large-scale nature of the interface creates a novel interactive system for music students. However, it is limited to the GPS resolution: an accuracy of 1-3 meters and a measurement every second. Given its scale, this is not necessarily problematic but it negates the possibility of using the interface in ‘real time’ since the rate of harmonic change would be slower than almost all styles and genres of music.

Chew’s [11] MuSA.RT Opus 2 interactive system for tonal and harmonic visualisation differs from the above approaches in two significant ways. Firstly, tonal and harmonic space is navigated purely through performance as opposed to user gestures. Input from a MIDI stream is parsed with a tonal induction algorithm which controls the movement of long term and short term ‘centres of effect’, and ‘closest triad’ on the visualisation. Secondly, the tonal and harmonic space is represented with a sophisticated nested spiral array model in contrast to the matrix-based tonnetz models described above. The resulting interface allows performers and audiences to visualise in detail the tonal landscape of a piece of music as it evolves.

1.2. Relation to Previous Work

With the above approaches in mind, we present an interface for users to intuitively navigate a tonnetz model without the need for specific prior skills or knowledge. It is important for such interfaces to be founded on musicologically convincing harmonic pitch models as they give structure in the audio feedback to the user. Since Chew’s Spiral Array model [11] is intended to visualise performances, it does not seem a good candidate for a gestural interface. The complex nature of the spiral structure is unlikely to be easy to navigate intuitively with simple gestures. [9] presents intuitive and simple interactions (in conjunction with performance) but does not seek to engage with music theoretical concepts. [6] notes the didactic importance of whole-body gestures, but reports the physical limitation they can entail on harmonic transitions around a physical tonnetz. Therefore, we propose an interface with a richer set of gestures to navigate a harmonic pitch space, thus reducing any physical limitations and giving users flexible and intuitive interaction.

2. THE TONNETZ

2.1. Musicological Perspectives

A brief overview of harmonic and pitch spaces is useful at this point. Both map chords or notes into a multidimensional space such that objects close together in the space are closely related musically. However, whereas pitch space maps individual notes into a space [2], harmonic space maps whole chords, typically represented by a root pitch [6]. Often useful systems are an amalgamation of the two, with the objects in the space representing individual pitches that can be grouped into chords [12].

Figure 2. A section of Longuet-Higgins’ infinite tonnetz ordered by major thirds and perfect fifths.

The dimensionality and complexity of harmonic spaces can vary considerably. Simple spaces map chords onto an infinite x - y plane [2] (Figure 2), referred to as a tonnetz or tone grid, ordered by fifths or thirds. A more complex tonnetz is at the core of Neo-Riemannian theory and consists of tessellated equilateral triangles with triads formed from the pitches at points of each triangle. Here, chord progressions are described by a combination of just three core transformation functions [12]. The dimensionality of a tonnetz can be increased to form 5-dimensional toroidal spaces, accounting for octave equivalence [13]. Similarly, octave equivalence is often described with spiral structures, as exhibited by [11].

Since the proposed interface aims to be intuitive and easy to navigate with gestures, a complex, high-dimensional harmonic space is rejected in favour of a simpler construct. It is important that a user can easily relate between the harmonic and physical spaces, so a three-dimensional matrix-based construct is presented in Section 2.3 as the musicological basis for the interface.

2.2. Root Progression Theories

A simple three-dimensional harmonic space demands a compact music theoretical grounding, as a complex model for harmony would map poorly onto a low dimensional harmonic space. Root progression theories [3, 4, 5] are extremely compact and often powerful models for tonal harmony, collapsing harmonies to a single note (root) [3] to explain harmonic progression. A permissible set of root transitions by consonant intervals (major thirds and sixths, minor thirds and sixths, and perfect fourths and

fifths) is defined [3] and subsequently categorised into symmetrically opposed groups: dominant and subdominant [4, 5], to explain tonal harmony. Compared to functional approaches to harmony this generates a far more compact set of six (paired) permissible harmonic transitions. This small set lend themselves to simple tonnetz architectures since the three pairs of transitions can be represented on three axes. As such, the proposed interface orders its three axes by major thirds, minor thirds, and perfect fifths. Each axis can be interpreted as representing dominant root progressions in one direction (e.g. a descending fifth) and subdominant progressions in the other (e.g. an ascending fifth) [c.f 4].

Figure 3. The 3D Tonnetz with the six labelled root progression vectors and pivot and triad notes in red and blue respectively.

2.3. The 3D Tonnetz

The 3D Tonnetz forming the musical model for the interface is based on an amalgamation of two common two-dimensional tonnetze. Longuet-Higgins’ tonnetz [2] (Figure 2) consists of a matrix of major thirds and perfect fifths, whilst *Harmony Space’s* tonnetz [6] (Figure 1) comprises of major and minor thirds. Bearing intervallic invertibility in mind, these intervals form the set of permissible consonant root transitions outlined in Section 2.2 [4]. Figure 3 maps this set of six root transitions as vectors to form the 3D Tonnetz for this interface. Note that the *x-y* plane forms *Harmony Space’s* tonnetz [6], and the *y-z* plane Longuet-Higgins’ tonnetz [2].

The 3D Tonnetz poses some interesting structural properties, lending it specifically to a musicologically grounded gestural interface. A single node can be selected as a pivot note (red) from which six permissible transitions to other nodes along the *x*, *y* or *z*-axes of the tonnetz can be made in accordance with [4]. From the pivot node, two triad nodes (blue) on the *x-y* plane can be selected from adjacent nodes to form six major or minor triads,

expanding harmonic options available to users for creative purposes.

For example, from the pivot note C (highlighted in red in Figure 3), E and G can be selected as triad notes (in blue) to form a C major triad, E♭ and G for C minor, and E♭ and A♭ for an A♭ major triad. In theory, diminished and augmented triads, as well as other non-diatonic sets of three pitches, could be selected from adjacent nodes, but for simplicity and usability, the proposed interface is restricted to major and minor triads. For visual clarity, selecting blue triad nodes adjacent on the *z*-axis is also prohibited.

2.4. Musicological Visual Analysis

Harmonic pitch spaces are useful tools for visualising the harmonic landscape of a piece of music. The root progression architecture of the 3D Tonnetz lends itself in particular to visual musicological analyses for the Classical (strongly favouring cycle of fifths progressions) and Romantic eras (with a wider variety of harmonic progressions). Two brief demonstrations are given below, mapping the root progressions of a few phrases onto the harmonic space defined in Section 2.3.

Figure 4. A visualisation of Beethoven’s Piano Sonata, Op. 27 No. 2, bars 1-9.

2.4.1. Beethoven’s Piano Sonata Op. 27 No. 2

The opening two phrases of Beethoven’s ‘Moonlight Sonata’ are a relatively straightforward example of how a tonal piece of music maps onto the 3D Tonnetz (Figure 4). Although the initial root progression is a descending third (C# - A or $i^7 - VI$), the majority of progressions operate along the fifths axis. The undulation between C# (i) and G# (V) in bars 5-7 gives way to a cycle of fifths towards a perfect cadence in E major, represented by a series of forward steps along the *z*-axis in the space. The progression from D (II♭) to G# (V) is conceived as a leap of two minor thirds along the *y*-axis, skipping F.

Figure 5. A visualisation of Brahms' Clarinet Sonata, Op. 120 No. 1, bars 5-12.

2.4.2. Brahms Clarinet Sonata Op. 120 No. 1

By contrast, the first subject of Brahms' Clarinet Sonata in F minor is strongly characterised by its movement around the x - y plane (Figure 5). The initial Brahmsian chain of falling thirds (F – Db – Bb – Gb) manifests itself in a down - left - down motion in the harmonic space. The more adventurous romantic harmony requires a series of leaps from Gb (IIb) to C (V) to Db (VI) and finally to G (V of v). Although more complex than Figure 4 in terms of spatial movement, the movements along the z -axis at the end give a clear visual indicator of the cadential closure of the phrase.

3. THE INTERFACE

The interactive interface comprises of three distinct components. A graphical representation gives users visual feedback of their position in the 3D Tonnetz (as described in Section 2.3), a colour-tracking system captures two-handed gestures from users, and a simple system gives audio feedback over MIDI.

Figure 6. The red and blue controllers in front of a projection of the 3D Tonnetz.

The interface setup is comprised of the graphical representation of the 3D Tonnetz (Figure 7) projected onto a black sheet, with the user holding two LED-lit Ping-Pong

balls mounted on controllers each with on/off button switches (Figure 6). To aid users, a small graphic of the locations of both balls can be shown in the lower right of the display or on a separate screen (Figure 8).

Figure 7. The graphical representation for the three-dimensional tonnetz rendered in Processing.

3.1. Visualisation of the 3D Tonnetz

The graphical representation of the harmonic pitch space was written in Processing¹ with OPENGL rendering (Figure 7). Nodes built with object-oriented programming represent pitches, displaying the corresponding note names. Users are presented with *Harmony Space's* tonnetz [6] on the x - y plane of the matrix, with Longuet-Higgins' tonnetz [2] going 'into' the screen on the y - z axis. Note names update with respect to the pivot pitch, maintaining intervallic relations for adjacent pitches. However, non-adjacent pitches are written enharmonically with the fewest possible number of accidentals. Nodes selected as the pivot and triad nodes are lit red and blue respectively, with the corresponding x - y plane highlighted. To give users the impression of moving through a physical space, the camera viewpoint tracks pivot note transitions with smooth glides.

3.2. Gestural Recognition

A gesture tracking system for the interactive interface is required to recognise two-armed gestures in three-dimensional space in real time and update the graphical representation. In selecting a tracking system, further preference was given to systems that were low-cost, preferably to be run from a laptop with an in-built webcam. Three methods were trialled for the interface: Oliver's [14] MANO controller, a detailed hand gesture recognition system; *blobscanner*², a hand-tracking library written in the Processing environment; and a purpose built colour-tracking system written in the Max/Jitter³ programming environment to track LED-lit hand-held controllers. The MANO controller is able to pick up detailed hand gestures without time lag, but requires a restrictive backlit, black background setup, which ties the user to a small area, in a similar manner to a touch-screen controller.

¹ <http://processing.org/>

² <https://code.google.com/p/blobscanner/>

³ <http://cycling74.com/products/max/video-jitter/>

Blobscanner is less restrictive in setup, but time lag makes it impractical for true real-time interactions with musical spaces. The purpose built Max/Jitter colour tracking system was chosen for the interactive system since it is unrestrictive in setup, fast and accurate, as well as being low-cost since it does not require specialised motion tracking equipment. Furthermore, button switches on the LED controllers provide additional functionality over hand gesture recognition systems as they can instantly be turned on or off.

Figure 8. The ‘clock face’ triad selection interface.

The system tracks red and blue LED-lit Ping-Pong balls mounted on non-reflective controllers, held in each of the users hands. Video is captured with a webcam set to a low exposure time to maximize the difference in brightness between the LED light and the background. For *up down, left* and *right* gestures, x and y co-ordinates are obtained by finding the centre point of a bounding box of all the coloured pixels defined within a specified RGB range. For example, the red bounding box selected pixels with red values of $0.5 - 1$, blue: $0 - 0.2$ and green: $0 - 0.2$. For *forward* gestures, the width of the bounding box is chosen to represent the size of the ball, and so movement through the z -axis. An alternative solution is to take the area of the box to map onto the z -axis. However, since the area has an inverse-quadratic relationship with distance from the camera, and the width only an inversionally proportional relationship, width maps better for the interface.

To map gestures to navigate the red node (as described in Section 2.3) around the tonnetz, *up, down, left, right* and *forward* messages are triggered after the red ball passes a threshold, which incorporates hysteresis to avoid spurious repeat triggers. Messages are only triggered once, until the red ball passes back through the threshold. *Back* messages are triggered when the red ball is turned off.

Gestures with the blue ball control the two blue nodes (described in Section 2.3) to select triads on the x - y plane. The angle between the blue ball and the centre of the screen is calculated, creating a ‘clock face’ interface with regions representing different triads (Figure 8). A region is selected when the blue ball moves into the region, or is turned on in that region. A ‘play’ message is triggered whenever the blue ball is turned on or when it has changed region.

As such, the functions of navigation (the red ball) and triad selection (the blue ball) are separated between the controllers. When triggered, all messages are sent over Open Sound Control (OSC) to the graphical representation running on Processing.

3.3. Audio Feedback

Audio output for the interface is governed by OSC messages sent from Processing to Max/MSP, which triggers various MIDI messages to an internal MIDI synthesizer application. Simply outputting the three notes of the triad selected in the tonnetz gives little control over inversion and creates weak voice leadings with parallel fifths whenever consecutive root position chords are played. To counteract this undesirable effect the triad is first converted to root position and transposed to several octaves simultaneously, generating a total of 19 MIDI notes. The large quantity of notes (somewhat counter intuitively) reduces the impact of parallel movement since the notes all have the same timbre and, therefore, cannot be easily streamed into distinct channels.

4. PRELIMINARY USER TEST

A simple preliminary user test was conducted to judge the quality of the interface as an interactive tool. In particular, the test aimed to identify any weaknesses in the gesture recognition system for future development and provide an indicator of how intuitive the interface was as a whole. Four participants were selected who had not used the interface before, with musical experience ranging from 0 to 8 years.

The test comprised of four stages. Firstly, the user was taught each of the six gestures for the red and blue controllers separately, making twelve gestures in total. For each gesture the number of attempts before a successful trigger was noted. In the second stage, four navigation tasks test how well the red pivot note can be moved around the 3D Tonnetz. The user was asked to move the red pivot note to a position up to two steps away, with any combination of *up, down, left, right, forward* and *back* gestures. Again, the number of attempts before successfully completing each task was recorded. In the third stage, the user was asked to follow three typical harmonic sequences represented as vector maps, for example, a descending cycle of fifths, or a falling third rising forth sequence. Finally, the user was given the opportunity to freely explore the interface.

4.1. Results

In general, the gesture recognition was successful for the novice participants: 79% of gestures triggering correctly on the first attempt and 98% by the second attempt for the initial instructional stage, which consisted of the user learning each gesture for each controller in turn (twelve in total). Of the four navigation tasks, one requiring a step forwards on the z -axis (a descending fifth) followed by a move in the x - y plane proved most difficult, with users requiring between 2 and 6 attempts. During harmonic sequence navigation tasks, forward steps (descending

fifths) also proved problematic with users making nearly twice as many errors in harmonic progressions with descending fifths compared to progressions that did not.

During the exploration stage, users exhibited a variety of gestural styles. The participant who had struggled most with the navigational tasks strongly preferred the blue 'clock face' controller, keeping the red relatively static. Two participants combined arm gestures with leg movement, either bending at the knees or lunging forwards with one leg to trigger the forward step.

4.2. Discussion

Although the interface appeared to be relatively intuitive with a high success rate in the instructional stage, the test identified the *forward* gesture as difficult to operate. Since this gesture corresponds to a descending fifth, a crucial progression in tonal music, a quick solution might be to use the 'red light off' gesture to descend a fifth and the forward gesture to ascend a fifth. However, a more permanent solution would be to improve the colour tracking along the *z*-axis, either by counting red or blue pixels to determine the size or adding a separate camera to the side of the user and simply track location.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The main contribution of this work is to provide the basic framework for an interface allowing users to navigate harmonic pitch space with gestures in three-dimensional space. The 3D Tonnetz based on [2, 6] and [3, 4, 5] was proposed as a model of harmony for the interface. A system to track two-handed gestures in real time was devised and simple audio feedback generated over MIDI.

A preliminary user study showed that some aspects of gesture recognition worked well but others, particularly *z*-axis motion (descending fifths), could be improved.

The strong didactic properties of the installation [c.f. 6] can be utilised by music students and teachers in conjunction with music theory, analysis and composition studies.

Furthermore, since the 3D Tonnetz is grounded firmly on root progression theories [3, 4, 5], the interface can be usefully applied to the field of music analysis. Empirical studies [5, 15] have shown that root progressions differ fundamentally between pre-tonal and tonal music. As such, the interface could provide an interesting visual tool to map these two genres of music for comparison.

Finally, with development to the audio system, the interface could be used in musical performances, both allowing performers to use gestures rather than instruments and for audiences to visualise musical performances.

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